

Austria Country Profile

Q3/2023

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Please note: The WG does not claim that the projects, activities, and infrastructures listed below are complete. This report represents a status quo. It is, however, updated on a regular basis and thus strives for the most accurate monitoring possible.

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Table of contents

1. Is there a current policy on open and FAIR science in place?	5
1.1. Is there a current policy regarding publications in place?	11
1.2. Is there a current policy regarding data/services in place?	12
1.3. Is there a current policy regarding research evaluation in place?	13
1.4. Is there a current policy regarding open learning in place?	14
2. Are there references to EOSC in the current policies?	15
2.1. Is funding or criteria for funding mentioned (with regards to EOSC)?	15
2.2. Is there a national contact point for open science?	15
2.3. Is there a national contact point for EOSC?	15
3. Current e-infrastructure that has the potential to be federated/accessible to the EOSC	16
4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) – Supporting Graphics	20
5. Annexes	26
Annex A: Data repositories/data centers	26
Annex B: Publication/document servers	29

Current policy on open and FAIR science

1. Is there a current policy on open and FAIR science in place?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
<p>Open Science Policy Austria In February 2022, the Open Science Policy Austria was adopted during a joint presentation to the Council of Ministers by the BMBWF, BMDW and BMK. With this presentation to the Council of Ministers and this Open Science Policy Austria, Austria is committed to the Open Science movement and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The vision of Open Science is to make scientific processes more open and effective and to use both scientific excellence and open innovative and applied research to address current challenges, which are very comprehensively presented in the Policies of the EU Commission and in the framework of the Global Sustainability Goals (UN SDGs).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More information and link to the document (currently only available in German): https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/HS-Uni/Hochschulgovernance/Leitthemen/Digitalisierung/Open-Science/Open-Science-Policy-Austria.html <p>Data Governance Act: As of 24 September 2023, the European Data Governance Act is applicable in all European member states. Goal: Promote the exchange of data, with due regard to GDPR regulation. The Act is part of the European Data Strategy. In Austria, the responsible body is the Federal Ministry of Finance (State Secretariat for Digitization and Telecommunications).</p> <p>Directive on the re-use of public sector information (PSI), now called Open Data Directive The European Open Data and PSI Directive provides the legal basis for the re-use of public sector data and sets a minimum set of rules. Focus is on non-personal data that are made freely available in the public interest.</p> <p>The Commission Implementing Regulation lays down a list of specific high-value datasets and the arrangements for their publication and re-use became effective on 09.02.2023 (IR (EU) 2023/138). Details see:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2023.019.01.0043.01.ENG <p>Some technical information for the implementation of the Directive in Austria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to § 11 IWG 2022, open data and thus also high-value datasets must be linked to the Austrian data portal data.gv.at, unless this requires a disproportionate effort (cf. adding data https://www.data.gv.at/daten/daten-hinzufuegen/) and for this purpose must be described in their core elements based on the Austrian standard metadata data.gv.at (cf. https://go.gv.at/ogdmetade). More detailed information on the provision of open data by the administration can be found in the Open Government Data (OGD) framework (cf. https://go.gv.at/ogdframede) and in the document "Wie erhöhen wir den Nutzen offener Daten in den nächsten 10 Jahren": https://www.data.gv.at/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/Wie-erhoehen-wir-den-Nutzen-offener-Daten-in-den-naechsten-10-Jahren_20230619.pdf • In the case of high-value datasets, the keyword "HighValueDataset" must also be indicated accordingly in the metadata for the dataset in question according to the specifications of the Austrian data portal data.gv.at. In this way, the criteria uniformly specified by the European data portal data.europa.eu can be fulfilled by the Austrian data portal data.gv.at. • High-value datasets that have already been published can be accessed via data.gv.at using this filter: https://www.data.gv.at/suche/?documentFilter%5B0%5D=HighValueDataset <p>A selection of relevant data providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data.gv.at: https://www.data.gv.at/. Is the central portal for public sector data • Open Data Portal Austria: https://www.opendataportal.at. The Open Data Portal Austria serves as a central platform for open data in the areas of business, culture, NGO/NPO, research and civil society in Austria. • GeoSphere-Austria Data Hub: https://data.hub.zamg.ac.at/ 		

- Mobilitydata.gv.at platform: <https://mobilitaetsdaten.gv.at/>. Serves as national access point of Austria for mobility data and is an implementation of the [national ITS-law](#). It's a centralised one-stop-shop to significantly simplify the connection of local data providers and international service providers by granting access to information on existing data and use conditions (metadata)
- INSPIRE Geoportal Österreich: <https://geoportal.inspire.gv.at>
 - Inspire.gv.at: <https://www.inspire.gv.at/>. Portal for spatial data
- AMDC - Austrian Micro Data Center [NB: not open data]: <https://www.statistik.at/services/tools/services/amdc-mikrodaten-fuer-die-wissenschaft>. The Austrian Microdata Center of Statistik Austria offers data protection-compliant access to microdata. The data remain at Statistik Austria, and only a virtual desktop infrastructure is provided for research projects. Not only data of Statistik Austria can be researched via the AMDC, but also other administrative and register data - provided that these are released for use in the AMDC by the respective department.

Digital Austria Act

The Digital Austria Act passed on June 1, 2023. More information see: <https://www.digitalaustria.gv.at/downloads.html>

Open Science policies by funding organizations

The largest national funding agency for basic research, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), is committed to support open and FAIR science through its open access policy to publications and to research data (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/>). 82% of all publications resulting from FWF projects are openly accessible. See also: [Compliance Monitoring 2021](#) report. Since 2019, the FWF requires a [data management plan \(DMP\)](#) supplemental to all approved grant proposals. The FWF has defined a minimum set of questions that comprise the DMP and that are to be addressed in the DMP template. The FWF DMP is in line with Science Europe's "[Core Requirements for Data Management Plans](#)".

The WWTF, the Vienna Science and Technology Fund, released an Open Science Policy in March 2022: <https://wwtf.at/funding/our-principles/downloads/open-access-and-open-science-policy>

Research data management policies in Austrian universities

Nine universities in Austria have policies for research data management in place, encouraging in these policies open science practices and the adoption of the FAIR principles:

- [Medical University Graz](#)
- [Medical University Vienna](#)
- [Graz University of Technology](#)
- [TU Wien](#)
- [University of Graz](#)
- [University of Innsbruck](#)
- [University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna](#)
- [University of Vienna](#)
- [WU \(Vienna University of Economics and Business\)](#)

Active projects funded by the BMBWF

In June 2022, the BMBWF released the call "(Digitale) Forschungsinfrastrukturen". 28 projects are being funded with a total of 40 million Euros. The following submissions with data relation were approved:

- Austrian Research Information and Service Network (ARI&Snet): The project will establish an Austrian network infrastructure for research data management, shared services and accessible research information embedded in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The project consortium consisting of 14 universities, FWF, WWTF, FFG und Natural History Museum Vienna aims to establish an association that coordinates the concerns of the entire national research landscape based on a sustainable set of participation rules, rights and obligations of the participants. Project duration: 01.09.2023-30.06.2026.
- Cloud4GEO: In the project, a federated cloud infrastructure integrated into the EOSC will be developed for the interdisciplinary use of geoscientific data in research and education. The project will link existing storage and data processing capacities at the Earth Observation Data Center

(EODC GmbH), GeoSphere Austria, the Vienna Scientific Cluster, and UIBK with computer systems of the participating universities and extend them according to a concept for the collaborative use of satellite data, ground observations, and computer simulations. Access to and use of the data will be significantly simplified by a single sign-on procedure and new open source software solutions. This will enable scientists and students to work with large amounts of data in an interdisciplinary way. This is the basis for excellent research and education in such important cross-cutting topics as climate change and the energy transition.

- Shared RDM Services and Infrastructure: <https://forschungsdaten.at/sharedrdm/>. The goal of the project is to create a framework to offer selected tools and infrastructures in the field of Research Data Management (RDM) as shared services for Austrian universities and research institutions. This bundling of different expertise creates a sensible use of resources and promotes interoperability, standardization, and the connection to international initiatives. The project is carried out in the spirit of the EOSC initiative and thus contributes to an even more reliable and simpler re-use of research output. Project duration: 1.7.2023-30.6.2026. Project consortium: 12 Austrian universities.

In 2019, the national call "Digital and social transformation" was launched by the BMBWF with selected digitization projects at public universities for the period 2020 to 2024, including activities connected to FAIR and EOSC. (NB: This is an excerpt out of 34 projects in total - selection due to open science relevance):

- Austrian Data Lab and Services (ADSL): <https://forschungsdaten.at/en/austrian-datalab-and-services/>. The ADLS project was set up to promote and facilitate collaborative work between universities, especially in the fields of data science and high performance computing (HPC). It aims to provide easy access to a nationwide network of applications in a federal opt-in model. In particular, the focus lies on increasing user-friendliness and saving time for researchers, teachers and students in the course of using computing resources.
- Austrian Neuro Cloud: <https://uni-salzburg.elsevierpure.com/de/projects/austrian-neuro-cloud>. Austria has an internationally competitive large-scale equipment infrastructure in the field of cognitive neuroscience, the potential of which is to be fully exploited through Austria-wide networking. The Austrian NeuroCloud will create a cross-location, open environment for the storage, management, and evaluation of neuro-cognitive data. The Austrian NeuroCloud thus creates a use case in the area of an extremely data-intensive research field that fulfils the vision of the European Open Science Cloud.
- Austrian Transition to Open Access II (AT2OA2): <https://at2oa.at/en/home.html>. The measures from AT2OA will be continued with the aim of concluding further Open Access agreements with publishers and setting up a data hub to process publication data from various sources. This can be used for Austria-wide OA monitoring and to support negotiations with scientific publishers and support the reporting system of the universities by making the data reusable for statistical verification systems, annual reports and the like. The use of alternative metrics will help answer the question of whether OA increases the visibility of scientific publications.
- codeAbility: <https://codeability.uibk.ac.at/index-en.html>. CodeAbility Austria creates teaching and learning environments in order to enable students of all subjects to receive high-quality and individual programming training.
- Digitale Landwirtschaft - Interuniversitäres PhD-Kolleg und digitale Versuchsfarmen.
- Digitize! Computational Social Sciences in the digital and social Transformation": <https://digitize-transformation.at/en/>. Digitize! is a cooperative digitalisation project in which various social sciences collaborate with data scientists, legal scholars and experts in research ethics.
- DiTAH - Digitale Transformation der Österreichischen Geisteswissenschaften: <https://www.ditah.at/>. The aim of this project is to establish and prepare the methods and approaches developed in the Digital Humanities in such a way that they can be transferred into the everyday use of research and education in the humanities.
- Image+: <https://www.angewandtekunstgeschichte.net/forschung/image-platform-for-open-art-education>. Image+ Platform for Open Art Education" is an Austrian image and image research platform to improve the quality of teaching.
- LEFO - Lehr- und Forschungsinfrastruktur für Digitale Künste an Hochschulen (Infrastructures for Digital Arts Teaching and Research in Higher Education: https://www.donau-uni.ac.at/de/forschung/projekt/U7_PROJEKT_4294970090. This project focuses on new interactive

interfaces and displays, which enable multimodal access to databases and multisensory analysis of the archived works. Within the concept of a living archive, students, researchers and teaching staff will be able to actively work on the database.

- Open Education Austria Advanced: <https://www.openeducation.at/>. Open Education Austria Advanced is a project of Austrian universities for the joint development of a national infrastructure for Open Educational Resources (OER) (project duration 01.03.2020-28.02.2024). It is an attempt to link services of e-learning centers, central IT services and libraries of the partner universities in order to support teachers in the creation of OER materials for self-study and teaching. The project aims at a gradual increase in the quality of teaching and learning, as well as the visibility of good-practice materials within the respective discipline.
- RIS Synergy: <https://forschungsdaten.at/en/ris/>. In order to digitise administrative processes, the IT systems of funding organisations and research institutions need to be connected, which would make it possible to improve data quality and conserve resources on all sides. New developments in the digital systems of the FWF (elane, PROFI, final project reports) offer an excellent opportunity.
- TransIT: <https://www.tunnellinghub.at/#project>. In the TransIT project (Platform for Digital Transformation in Civil Engineering and Tunneling), research groups are working in a multidisciplinary manner with complementary expertise on the implementation of digitization topics in civil engineering and tunneling. For this purpose, a virtual research platform, the Digital Tunneling Hub, is being created at the University of Leoben.

Completed projects funded by the BMBWF (formerly HRSM projects)

- Austrian Transition to Open Access: <https://at2oa.at/en/home.html>
- CCCA Data Centre, CCCA: <https://data.ccca.ac.at>, <https://ccca.ac.at>.
- e-Infrastructures Austria: <https://e-infrastructures.univie.ac.at/>
- e-Infrastructures Austria Plus: <https://www.e-infrastructures.at/en>
- FAIR Data Austria: <https://forschungsdaten.at/en/fair-data-austria/>
- GEOCLIM: <https://wegcenter.uni-graz.at/en/research/arsclisys-research-group/projects/geoclim/>.
- IDE@S: Innovative Data Environments: <https://www.tugraz.at/projekte/ideas/home/>
- Integriertes Datenmanagement: <https://biotechmedgraz.at/en/programs/shared-infrastructure/infrastructure-call-2016/>

Active EU projects fostering Open Science, FAIR and the EOSC (including Partners from the Austrian RPOs)

- DISSCo: <https://www.dissco.eu/>. The Distributed System of Scientific Collections is a new world-class Research Infrastructure (RI) for Natural Science Collections. The DISSCo RI aims to create a new business model for one European collection that digitally unifies all European natural science assets under common access, curation, policies and practices.
- EOSC Focus: <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project>. The project will support the co-programmed EOSC Partnership in delivering its mission of establishing Open Science as the “new normal” and achieving the key objectives, which are outlined in the Memorandum of Understanding between the European Union and the EOSC Association (EOSC-A).
- Skills4EOSC: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>. Goal is to unify the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, in order to accelerate the upskilling of European researchers and data professionals in the field of FAIR and Open Data, intensive-data science and Scientific Data Management.
- EOSC Future: <https://eoscfuture.eu/>. EOSC Future will build on the existing baseline for the European Open Science Cloud to deliver a platform with a durable set of user-friendly components that are designed for the long haul. We will adopt a system-of-systems approach to the EOSC platform, linking together other research portals, resources and services to respond to the data needs of a wide range of researchers.
 - RDA/EOSC Future Cross-disciplinary Science Adoption: GIGAR-V “Guiding Infrastructure Governance and Controlled Vocabularies requirement”. The core objective is to create a holistic framework of recommendations enabling harmonization and alignment between different concept vocabularies, also including the taxonomy approach as reference codes,

allowing for greater interoperability of related data resources. <https://eoscfuture-grants.eu/provider/research-data-alliance/rda-open-call-cross-disciplinary-science-adoption-grants-2>.

- EuroCC: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/>. Goal: to develop in European countries National Competence Centers (NCC) in High Performance Computing (HPC), Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. This NCC will be the contact point for academia, industry and public organisations for collaborations in HPC, Big Data and AI projects, and the NCC will document, map and coordinate activities in these areas. Within the project, the tasks are (i) training and skills development, (ii) technology transfer/business development, (iii) academia-industry collaborations, (iv) mapping of HPC/Big Data/AI competences and (v) facilitation of access to expertise and resources.
- FAIRiCUBE: <https://fairicube.nilu.no/>. The project will pave the way for a crosscutting platform and framework for data ingestion, provision, analysis, processing, and dissemination, to unleash the potential of environmental, biodiversity and climate data through dedicated European data spaces. Focus will be on the development of tools that enable users who are not intimately familiar with the worlds of Earth Observation and machine learning to scope the requirements and costs of their desired analyses.
- TIER2 (enhancing Trust, Integrity and Efficiency in Research through next-level Reproducibility) will increase reproducibility of scientific research results that will bring trust, integrity, and efficiency to the European Research Area (ERA) and the global Research and Innovation (R&I) system. The project will boost knowledge on reproducibility, create tools, engage communities, implement interventions and policy across different contexts to increase re-use and overall quality of research results. TIER2 aims to build an evidence-based on the extent and efficacy of existing reproducibility practices and co-create new tools to enhance reproducibility across diverse contexts. <https://tier2-project.eu/>

Completed EU projects (including Partners from the Austrian RPOs)

- EOSC-Pillar: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>
- EOSC Secretariat: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/>
- ON MERRIT: <https://on-merrit.eu/>
- RDA Europe Adoption Grant: CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation - A Design Concept for OpenEO interface for climate projection data. Cooperation CCCA & TU Wien, 2019-2020
- SSHOC: <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

Networks fostering Open Science, Citizen Science, FAIR, EOSC, and PSI activities

- ABOL – Austrian Barcode of Life - ein Netzwerk für Biodiversität: <https://www.abol.ac.at/>
- Citizen Science Network Austria: <https://www.citizen-science.at/netzwerk> Österreich forscht: [Citizen Science Projekte - Österreich forscht \(citizen-science.at\)](https://www.citizen-science.at)
- dha – digital humanities Austria: <https://digital-humanities.at/de>
- DOI-Service Austria: <https://www.tuwien.at/bibliothek/doi-service-austria-orcid-austria> moved to the new website: <https://orcid-austria.org/>
- European Citizen Science Association (ECSA): <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/>
- EOSC Support Office Austria: <https://eosc-austria.at/>
- GEO (Group on Earth Observation) – GEO Data Working Group: Review on Data Sharing and Data Management Principles and crosswalk towards FAIR and Trust Principles. https://www.earthobservations.org/data_wg.php
- GO FAIR Austria office/FAIR Office Austria: <https://www.fair-office.at>
- KEMÖ - Kooperation E-Medien Österreich: [Austrian Academic Library Consortium \(KEMÖ\)](https://www.kemoe.at)
- Kulturerbe digital: <https://www.kulturerbe-digital.at>
- Kulturpool: <http://www.kulturpool.at/display/kupo/Home>
- OANA – Open Science Network Austria: <https://www.oana.at> (2012-2021; comment: restructured under the umbrella of uniko and under the title of "Open Science Austria (OSA)")
- Open Science Austria - OSA: <https://www.osa-openscienceaustria.at>
- Open Science - Lebenswissenschaften im Dialog: <https://www.openscience.or.at/de>

- ORCID Austria: <https://www.tuwien.at/kooperationen/orcid/en/home/>
- Plattform Registerforschung: <https://www.registerforschung.at/>
- RDA Austria: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-austria>

Other initiatives

On 17 April 2023, Austria joined ELIXIR as Observer, following approval by the ELIXIR Board. The ELIXIR Node in Austria will now begin to be established. ELIXIR Nodes bring together organisations that provide bioinformatics services, such as universities and research institutes. The Austrian Node will be initially centred around the bioinformatics services of the University of Vienna, as well as the Medical University of Vienna, with planned expansion to other sites in future. The focus of the Austrian Node will be on services, training, computing, data management and data processing. More information see: <https://elixir-europe.org/news/austria-joins>

Open Science, RDM and Data Stewardship trainings

Certificate Course “Data Steward” at the University of Vienna:

In order to build skills and competences for the EOSC as well as research institutions in Austria, the Vienna University Library developed a formal part-time further education program – the [certificate course “Data Steward”](#). The contents are based on a previous certificate course “[Data Librarian](#)”, the results of the [FAIR Data Austria project](#) and similar programs such as [DataTrain](#) and [Zertifikatskurs FDM](#) in Germany. The course supports both existing staff and new hires in generic and domain-specific data stewardship roles in acquiring knowledge and key competences to perform the tasks of data stewards at research institutions. The course was designed following three guiding principles – competence acquisition (1), peer-to-peer learning (2) and community building (3). The first round began with 25 emerging data stewards from 10 countries in October 2022. The next round will start in October 2023. More information at: <https://www.postgraduatecenter.at/en/programs/communication-media/data-steward/>

Publications related to Open Science, RDM, FAIR, and EOSC:

- EOSC Austria Annual Activity Report 2022/2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063171>
- Rat für Forschung und Technologieentwicklung. Bericht zur wissenschaftlichen und technologischen Leistungsfähigkeit Österreichs 2023. <https://fti-monitor.rfte.at/docs/pdf/L100012.pdf>
- Community-driven Governance of FAIRness Assessment” is one output of the TF FAIR Metrics & Data Quality that is being submitted to Open Research Europe, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390482>
- Data Stewardship at Austrian Universities (2022): This report, in the form of a toolbox, presents data steward models, together with the required competences and training. It allows universities to choose the appropriate implementation strategy based on their characteristics needs. It is available for download under this [link](#).
- Empfehlungen für eine nationale Open Science Strategie in Österreich / Recommendations for a National Open Science Strategy in Austria (Final version including comments and annotations of the public consultation). 2020. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4109242>
- EOSC Pillar: Survey for research infrastructures and their FAIRness level. It addressed Austrian RI organisations, universities, and policy makers (2019/2020). The report was published and is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937318>.
 - The data of the study is available at: https://data.aussda.at/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.11587/VOSVGKFTI-Strategie2030_Gesamtost. Universitätsentwicklungsplan2022-2027_UniNETZ-Optionenbericht
- Mayer, Katja (2022) Open Access im Wandel. Infrastrukturen, Monitoring und Governance als zentrale Elemente einer erfolgreichen Transformation. Baseline Report zur Open Access Transformation in der Wissenschaft. Technischer Bericht. Wien. <https://repository.fteval.at/596/>
- National survey of researchers and their data: In 2015, 36.000 researchers at Austrian universities were asked about their practices and requirements for research data management. Results:
 - Researchers and Their Data. Results of an Austrian Survey (PDF Full Report/en): https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail_object/o:409318

- o Executive Summary: Researchers and Their Data. Results of an Austria-wide survey (en): http://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail_object/o:408001

1.1. Is there a current policy regarding **publications** in place?

Yes	No	In planning
x		

According to the [Open Science Policy Austria](#), open scholarly publishing must become the standard approach as soon as possible. To drive this momentum, research publications resulting from calls for projects that are publicly funded must be disseminated via open access platforms, be it in journals, books or via an open public repository. Austrian universities are encouraged to ensure that publications by researchers working there are also under open licenses. To maintain these practices over time, the evaluation system for researchers and research institutions needs to be updated to reflect the principles and practices of open science. Changes in the way researchers are evaluated aim to give more weight to quality over quantity, as outlined in the proposals of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) and the principles of the Leiden Manifesto. The scientific community must regain control over the publishing process in general, in accordance with the principles that govern open science and bibliodiversity are required. It must focus its efforts on those stakeholders who are working to develop a less concentrated publishing environment that is consistent with the principles of open and ethical access. *[Excerpt translated from the Open Science Policy Austria (page 10)]*

Open access policies in Austrian research institutions

- At this point, there are several institutional OA policies in place (see <https://www.oana.at/ueber-open-science/open-access-ressourcen/#c236283>).
- Several Austrian institutions support alternative publication formats and platforms such as Open library of humanities, SciPost, DOAJ, OAPEN, Open Knowledge Maps: <https://oana.at/nationale-aktivitaeten/support-von-infrastrukturen/>; <https://oapen.org/funders/7589935-fwf-austrian-science-fund>
- Implementation of institutional publication servers: An overview (from 2018) is available in the following publication: Bauer, B., & Ferus, A. (2018). Österreichische Repositorien in OpenDOAR und re3data.org: Entwicklung und Status von Infrastrukturen für Green Open Access und Forschungsdaten. Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare, 71(1), 70–86. <https://doi.org/10.31263/voebm.v71i1.2037>

Strategy towards Plan S

- Since 2021, the Open Access Policy of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), which is one of the first members of cOAlition S, is in line with Plan S. The BMBWF supports Plan S (see e.g. Anfragebeantwortung durch den Bundesminister für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung Dr. Heinz Faßmann zu der schriftlichen Anfrage (933/J) der Abgeordneten Dr. Helmut Brandstätter, Kolleginnen und Kollegen an den Bundesminister für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung betreffend Plan S: https://www.parlament.gv.at/PAKT/VHG/XXVII/AB/AB_00935/imfname_791658.pdf).
- Furthermore, a working group in the framework of the Forum of Austrian University Libraries (ubifo) is currently developing guidelines for an institutional implementation of Plan S at the Austrian universities.

Other successful initiatives and projects promoting open access to publications in Austria

- The national funding agency FWF was one of the first funding agencies worldwide to establish an open access policy to publications in 2004: <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/open-access-to-peer-reviewed-publications/open-access-publication-models/>. Today, almost all publications resulting from FWF grants see [Austrian Science Fund \(FWF\) Open Access Compliance Monitoring](#)) are open access.
- The Austrian Academic library consortium (KEMÖ) together with the FWF was the first consortium worldwide to negotiate a transformative open access agreement in 2014 and since then several open access agreements have been concluded so that Austrian researchers can publish their research results open access and free of costs. <https://www.konsortien.at/>

- In March 2022, the [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#) was published. The action plan proposes to develop and expand a sustainable, community-driven Diamond OA scholarly communication ecosystem. It is endorsed by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF).
- In 2016, a working group of the Open Science Network Austria (OANA) published the "Recommendations for the Transition to Open Access in Austria" which helped to further Open Access to publications in Austria.
- Ministry-funded project [Austrian Transition to Open Access II](#) (AT2OA2): The measures from AT2OA will be continued with the aim of concluding further Open Access agreements with publishers and setting up a data hub to process publication data from various sources. This can be used for Austria-wide OA monitoring and to support negotiations with scientific publishers and support the reporting system of the universities by making the data reusable for statistical verification systems, annual reports and the like.

1.1.1. If yes, does it include open access to publications ?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
See above, 1.1. Is there a current policy regarding publications in place?		

1.2. Is there a current policy regarding data / services in place?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		

1.2.1. If yes, does it include open access to data ?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		

According to the [Open Science Policy Austria](#), the aim is to ensure that data generated by publicly funded research in Austria have to comply with the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), that they have to be preserved and, whenever possible, made openly accessible to the public.

The goal is also to implement a mandatory open-access dissemination mandate for all data that has already been made available as part of publicly funded projects. Certain exceptions to this obligation will be allowed in accordance with the law, e.g., if the data in question are professional secrets, statistical secrets, labor and trade secrets, personal data, or content subject to copyright, as well as if the data are considered sensitive due to national security, defense, or public safety and health.

Considering the European Data Strategy, several European legal provisions regulate the reuse of research data, in particular the European Commission Recommendation on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information (revised 2018), the revised Directive on Open Data and the Reuse of Public Sector Information (Open Data and PSI RL 1024/2019), and the EU Copyright Directive, which applies to publicly funded research data and to which Austria subscribes. The aim is that research data can be re-used for commercial and non-commercial purposes, as long as it has been publicly funded and if it has been made publicly available by researchers, research institutions or research funding bodies via an institutional or thematic archive.

Furthermore, the European Data Strategy published in 2020 is intended to drive forward the creation of a single market for data. The aim is to increase the exchange and use of data within the EU and across sectors for the benefit of researchers, companies, and public administrations. This approach also forms the basis of the new European Research Area (ERA) to build a common science and technology space for the EU. Open Science and Open Data are essential tools for improving collaboration between researchers and innovators to enhance Austria's attractiveness as a location for the world's best talents. *[Excerpt translated from the Open Science Policy Austria (page 8)]*

Open Data as funders' requirement

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) expects open access to research data collected and/or analyzed using FWF funds for projects approved from 1 January 2019 onward: <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research->

[funding/open-access-policy/open-access-to-research-data/](#). Open access is mandatory for research data on which the research publications of the project are based. Further, since 2019, the FWF has a mandatory policy on research data management in place: <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/research-data-management/>

The WWTF states in its policy that it “does not require that all research data be made available. However, WWTF strongly encourages grantees to provide shareable research data according to each calls’ specifications and requirement”. More information see: https://wwtf.at/upload/wwtf_open-science-policy_09032022.pdf

1.3. Is there a current policy regarding **research evaluation** in place?

Yes	No	In planning
x		

According to the [Open Science Policy Austria](#), new ways of evaluating research will be explored, especially to accommodate open science practices. Publish-or-perish environments will be broken up and avoided. Open peer review practices are to be implemented in order to make the evaluation of scientific output more transparent. Despite years of intense criticism of so-called journal-based metrics, the impact factor of prominent journals still plays a significant role in the scientific community, especially when it comes to career planning. Increased transparency of evaluation processes of researchers and their applications should be ensured. Austria respects the goals of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), an international initiative that aims to establish metrics for evaluating scientific work. On the European level, the Leiden Manifesto should be mentioned in this context, which formulates similar intentions in the European context. *[Excerpt translated from the Open Science Policy Austria (page 4)]*

[DORA - San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment](#)

In 2012, a set of recommendations that addresses the need to change the way of how output of scientific research is evaluated by funding agencies, academic institutions, and other parties, was published and is referred to as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA Declaration). The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) and several Austrian research institutions signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA): See: [Austrian signatories](#).

[Hongkong Principles for assessing researchers](#)

The Hongkong Principles were formulated and endorsed at the 6th World Conference on Research Integrity in June 2019. The principles aim to help research institutions to minimise incentives that invite to engage in questionable research practices or worse. The Austrian Science Fund (FWF), WIFO and the Austrian Agency for Research Integrity [endorsed the principles](#).

[COARA - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#)

In July 2022, the agreement on reforming research assessment was published after a Stakeholder Assembly bringing together the 350+ organisations from 40+ countries having expressed interest in being involved in advancing research assessment. The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) and several Austrian research institutions commit to COARA and to working on the advancement of the current scholarly assessment system. See: [Austrian signatories](#)

FTEVAL

Note: The Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation (FTEVAL) is concerned with issues of research evaluation in Austria:

- <https://www.fteval.at/content/home/plattform/about/index.jsp?langId=2>
- <https://repository.fteval.at>
- Code of conduct: <https://repository.fteval.at/387/> and principles: https://www.fteval.at/content/home/standards/fteval_prinzipien/index.jsp?langId=2

FTEVAL is an association whose members are institutions from the fields of research, technology and innovation (RTI). It includes government ministries, agencies, research funding organisations, research institutes and consulting firms. Membership is open to all those involved in commissioning or carrying out evaluations in the field of RTI. The aim of the association is to further develop the culture and practice of evaluation in Austria in the field of RTI. The fteval platform regards evaluation as central to ongoing

improvement and strategic focus in RTI policy. A “good” culture of evaluation is both a prerequisite for and a result of “good” – i.e., efficient, transparent, and fair – policies. As declared in the mission statement: *“The mission of the Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation is to promote the quality, transparency and adequate coverage of evaluations, to improve strategic planning of research, technology and innovation (RTI) policy in Austria. The existing evaluation culture is evolving continuously, in consultation with decision makers in Austrian RTI policy.”*

Related Publication

- [available in German only] Janger, J. and T. König (2020). Forschungspolitik in Österreich. Zentrale Ansatzpunkte für eine Leistungssteigerung in der Grundlagenforschung

1.4. Is there a current policy regarding **open learning** in place?

Yes	No	In planning
x		

According to the [Open Science Policy Austria](#), the aspect of how knowledge is taught is also inseparably linked to an open society and an open science. The dissemination of knowledge is closely linked to the concept of open data.

Measurements:

- Austria would like to make its contribution to making the learning materials created in Austria publicly accessible in open formats in whatever form, for example on the basis of established open data standards. In a first step, the relevant repositories will be linked and thus made publicly accessible. In this way, Austria would like to make learning content available to the scientific community on the one hand, and on the other hand make learning more flexible and adapt it to individual needs.
- Universities and other extramural research institutions are therefore called upon both to create infrastructures to be able to deposit OER and to share them with others. Staff working at universities and universities of applied sciences should be encouraged to post and share their content in open formats where possible and appropriate.

The Forum New Media Austria (FNMA) has already prepared "Recommendations for the Integration of Open Educational Resources at Universities in Austria". The currently running project "Open Education Austria Advanced", in which several universities are involved, deals with the implementation of a corresponding infrastructure. Website: <https://fnma.at/>

[Excerpt translated from the *Open Science Policy Austria* (page 11)]

Active projects funded by the BMBWF

In 2019, a national call “Digital and social transformation” was launched by the BMBWF with selected digitization projects at public universities for the period 2020 to 2024, including activities connected to digitalization in teaching and learning. (NB: This is an excerpt - selection according to learning reference):

- iMooX: <https://imoox.at/mooc/?lang=en>. iMooX is currently operated by the TU Graz and is to be expanded both technically and organisationally. At present, cooperation is taking place by offering individual MOOCs. In the future, all participating universities are to offer any number of MOOCs to the Austrian educational landscape. Through a central Austria-wide platform, all universities can participate equally and the costs for maintenance and and operation can be minimised. "iMooX as a Service" is the declared goal.
- Learning Analytics: <https://learning-analytics.at/home/>. The project provides the first holistic and comprehensive view of the topic of Learning Analytics at Austrian universities and makes an important contribution to the development of functioning Learning Analytics methods in the university context. The development of appropriate tools in an interdisciplinary team ensures the innovation potential of the project results. The uniqueness of the project results primarily from the fact that the students themselves are at the center and benefit directly from the results.
- Open Education Austria Advanced: <https://www.openeducation.at/>. Goals: Solutions for Open Education Resources (OER) in the Austrian higher education sector: OERHub as a central meta-search engine for OER from the the higher education area; creation of local infrastructures at the

- partner universities; freely accessible qualification offers for OER certification for universities & teachers; knowledge transfer & dissemination between participating and interested universities.
- PASSt - Predictive Analytics Services für Studienerfolgsmanagement: <https://colab.tuwien.ac.at/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=6030634>. The project aims to make academic success measurable and predictable. The modelling implemented by means of supervised machine learning procedures modelling allows the prediction of academic success on an individual and aggregated level. In a further step, an agent-based simulation system to experiment with measures in simulation scenarios. The results help universities to better understand the mechanisms of success in higher education and to predict success at a future point in time.

2. Are there references to EOSC in the current policies?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
2.1. Is funding or criteria for funding mentioned (with regards to EOSC)?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
In the June 2022 call "(Digitale) Forschungsinfrastrukturen" released by the BMBWF there were clear references to EOSC. EOSC relevance also played a role in the selection criteria.		
2.2. Is there a national contact point for open science?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
<p>Austrian Federal Ministry of Education (BMBWF)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact at administrative level (Open Science Policy, EOSC at ministry level): Stefan Hanslik, Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, Head of Unit, Department V/3a; contact: stefan.hanslik@bmbwf.gv.at <p>Open Science Austria (OSA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact person: Lola Karner, Officer for Open Science Austria (OSA), at the Austrian University Conference (Uniko); lola.karner@uniko.ac.at • Website: https://www.osa-openscienceaustria.at 		
2.3. Is there a national contact point for EOSC?		
Yes	No	In planning
x		
<p>National structure/Mandated Organisation/Key coordination structure of EOSC in Austria</p> <p>The Austrian EOSC initiative started in 2021 after the foundation and first General Assembly of the EOSC Association.</p> <p>The ACONET Association[1] is the signatory of the Memorandum of Understanding with the EOSC Association and thus the Austrian EOSC Mandated Organisation. To carry out the work this entails towards the implementation of EOSC, however, ACONET Association has created a dedicated body, the EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA). ACONET Association's role can therefore be understood as legal representative with no operational plans or executive power over the EOSC-related tasks in Austria. This is done by the EOSC SOA, whose members include Austrian research performing organisations. Founded in 2021, EOSC SOA thus acts as the coordinator of EOSC activities in the country and as closest link to the EOSC Association. Its operational goals translate those of the EOSC Association into the national context. Contact: Paolo Budroni, paolo.budroni@tuwien.ac.at</p>		

[1] Not to be confused with the National Research and Education Network (ACOnet), originally funded by the Austrian Ministry of Science within the framework of the ACONET Association and was established in 1990 under the responsibility of TU Wien. Since 1992 ACOnet has been operated by the University of Vienna.

EOSC Support Office Austria (SOA)

EOSC SOA is managed by the Management Board, chaired each year by a member of the organisation on a rotational basis. For 2023, Heimo Rainer (heimo.rainer@nhm-wien.ac.at) from Natural History Museum in Vienna (NHMW) is the Board's chair.

The "EOSC Austria Annual Activity Report 2022/2023" describes the achievements in 2022 and the status quo per June 2023. More information see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063171>

Contact EOSC SOA: contact@eosc-austria.at

Website: <https://eosc-austria.at/>

EOSC Association Steering Board representative: Stefan Hanslik, Head of Unit of Technical Science at the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)

Email: stefan.hanslik@bmbwf.gv.at

3. Current e-infrastructure that has the potential to be federated / accessible to the EOSC

General remarks

Austria has several organizations that offer national generic and discipline-specific e-infrastructure services.

A large number of Austrian research institutions offer institutional publication servers for open access to research publications. In addition, there is a growing number of public institutions providing institutional data repositories. Access to content is generally open and free of charge. Use of the systems is subject to the applicable policies and terms of use of each system. There is currently no central access point (central entry point) to Austrian research results. The infrastructure landscape is based on distributed systems. For an overview, see Annex A (data repositories) and Annex B (publication repositories).

3.1. Data and computing infrastructures

Aggregating portal of services

- BMBWF research infrastructure database: The public database of the BMBWF provides an overview of national research infrastructures. It serves as an information platform and may be used to find and offer research infrastructures for new cooperation projects: <https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmbwf.gv.at/en>

Infrastructures providing domain specific (data) services

- AUSSDA (The Austrian Social Science Data Archive) is a data infrastructure for the social science community in Austria and offers a variety of research support services, primarily data archiving and help with data re-use. Ref.: <https://aussda.at/en/>. AUSSDA is the national Service Provider within CESSDA ERIC.
- BBMRI ERIC - <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>. BBMRI-ERIC is a distributed research infrastructure of biobanks and biomolecular resources. For its Member States, it provides expertise and services on a non-economic basis and facilitates access to collections of partner biobanks and biomolecular resources. BBMRI-ERIC is established for an unlimited period of time. The Central Executive Management Office is located in Graz, Austria.
- CCCA-DC (www.data.ccca.ac.at): Storage connected to the EODC cloud and VSC
- CLARIN. The Austrian Academy of Science is participating in CLARIN (ACDH-OEAW): Digital Humanities Austria (dha) is an open network of institutional partners in Austria joining efforts to realize a new understanding of humanities research in a digital environment. These efforts are an integral part of the Austrian commitment to the research infrastructure

	<p>consortia CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-EU, pan-European communities of practice organized as networks of centres sharing resources, tools and knowledge. Ref. http://digital-humanities.at/en</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CyVerse Austria. Provides life scientists with powerful computational infrastructure to handle huge datasets and complex analyses, thus enabling data-driven discovery. The extensible platforms provide data storage, bioinformatics tools, image analyses, APIs, and more. CyVerse Austria uses open source code from CyVerse US (University of Arizona). https://www.tugraz.at/sites/cat/home/ • EODC. www.eodc.eu Operates a virtualised, distributed earth observation (EO) data centre, providing collaborative IT infrastructure for archiving, processing, and distributing EO data. Together with its multi-national partners from science, the public and private sectors EODC fosters the use of satellite-derived geoinformation. Its focus ranges from scientific research to operational services in the areas of water resources and land monitoring, agricultural applications, and humanitarian aid and civil security. Infrastructures characteristics: Multi-Petabyte-scale storage (discs and tape) connected to the EODC cloud and to EODC • GEOCLIM Long Term Archive: EODC & CCCA-DC implemented a tape-based long-term archive on two locations at TU Wien and VSC <p>Network Infrastructures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACONet – the Austrian NREN (www.ACO.net) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ high performance network infrastructure (contract and infrastructure renewal finished June 2023) ○ member of GÉANT • Austrian Quantum Fiber Network (AQUnet) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FFG R&D infrastructure funding project coordinated by the ACONET Association ○ intended to complement and enable the (new) ACONet backbone infrastructure for CLONETS and EuroQCI-related research • EGI - With beginning of 2022, ACONET Association joined the EGI Foundation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The EGI is a European federation of e-Infrastructures, providing services, data, processing capabilities and knowledge from its partners to the scientific community. Its decentralised federated cloud architecture has been created as an 'Infrastructure as a Service' (IaaS), was built around open standards and is driven by the requirements of a scientific community. Scopes are to facilitate the (joint) access to general/specialised ICT resources for interested users at pan-European scale, to offer related training and thus to promote collaborative science and to increase the effectiveness of existing resources. While the first steps of this upcoming collaboration between EGI and Austrian entities will have to be discussed in 2022, several Austrian partners already participate together with EGI in the H2020 project EGI-ACE (coordinated by the EODC Earth Observation Data Centre, Vienna), developing an EOSC Compute platform and contributing to the implementation of the EOSC Data Commons. In this context, PaaS' will be provided to the EOSC, including data spaces with analytics tools and federated access services. • ACONet Identity Federation (eduID.at - member of eduGAIN)
<p>3.2. HPC infrastructures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Austrian e-infrastructure became part of the EuroHPC JU via assembly of an AT HPC Competence Centre and membership to the CINECA Consortium implementing LEONARDO • MACH-2 – The massively parallel shared memory supercomputer "MACH-2" is operated in the frame of a project by the Johannes Kepler University (JKU)

	<p>Linz on behalf of a consortium of several Austrian universities and research institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSC – The Vienna Scientific Cluster is a collaboration of several Austrian universities that provides supercomputer resources and corresponding services to their users, it is operated by TU Wien.
<p><i>3.3. Repositories and main components of the e-Infrastructure in Austria</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and computing infrastructures, data repositories, and publication servers, please refer to Annexes A and B. • PID-Services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DOI-Service Austria: https://www.tuwien.at/bibliothek/doi-service-austria-orcid-austria ○ ORCID Austria: https://orcid-austria.org/ https://www.tuwien.at/kooperationen/orcid/en/home/

EOSC AUSTRIA

– EOSC PROCESS-RELEVANT INFRASTRUCTURES

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) envisages the development of a federated European data infrastructure that integrates cloud solutions and services in the scientific sector and later extends these data and services to the public sector and industry.

The graphic visualises selected "EOSC process-relevant infrastructures" from Austria that are accessible via the Austrian research infrastructure database.

<https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmbwf.gv.at>

25

SELECTED RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

– OPEN FOR COLLABORATION

**Federal Ministry
Republic of Austria
Education, Science
and Research**

Graphic: Dr. Thorsten D. Barth, BMBWF 2022

**FORSCHUNGS
INFRASTRUKTUR
DATENBANK**

Infographic EOSC Austria -- EOSC process-relevant infrastructures (created by Torsten Barth, BMBWF):
https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmbwf.gv.at/img/cluster/EOSC-2022_AT_FI-DB.png

4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the Austrian EOSC initiative

The EOSC Support Office Austria Working Group “Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)” is a cornerstone of the EOSC ecosystem in Austria. Its primary objective is to develop and define measurable indicators to assess the success of EOSC at the national level and the alignment with the European level. The group has identified specific overarching goals for Austria and is working to develop indicators that will help to assess the readiness of Austria in achieving these goals. The KPIs are designed to serve as a steering instrument for targeted, impact-oriented further development and implementation of the EOSC. The KPI graphics below refer to the EOSC Support Office Austria and illustrate the objectives and achievements of the Austrian EOSC initiative as of 31 December 2022.

Graphic: EOSC-KPIs: Objectives at the SOA-level. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Scientific Impact

Community Building

We align institutions through our Austrian EOOSC partnership and implement support in our institutions.

2022
Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners of EOOSC SOA reference points in institutions of EOOSC SOA research support activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of signatories of the MoU number of reference points (headcounts) number of workshops, webinars, engagement activities 	all types	1 x per year

Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
	Internal	External	
Management Board (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> coLAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 ordinary partners 7 extraordinary partners 12 EOOSC reference points in these institutions 8 webinars, workshops, engagement activities

Graphic: EOOSC-KPIs: Scientific impact – Community Building. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Socio-economic Impact

Coordination

The EOOSC Support Office Austria coordinates the national EOOSC partnership efficiently.

Oct 2021
Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> standardised processes transparent voting processes regular meetings back-office staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> review of processes and structures frequency of internal meetings number of back office staff in FTEs 	all types	Evaluation period April 2025

Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
	Internal	External	
Management Board (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> coLAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 standardised processes 1 transparent voting process 44 regular meetings (in total) 1,5 FTEs back office staff funded by the BMBWF for 3 years (01.07.2022-30.06.2025)

Graphic: EOOSC-KPIs: Socio-economic impact – Coordination. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Socio-economic Impact

Diversity

We strengthen diversity within the EOSC Support Office Austria.

2022

Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

2025

Starting point for Social Network Analysis

Indicators		Methods		Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> diversity of partners 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> qualitative description of role and relevance of the partners Social Network Analysis 		all types	Every third year
Source of data		Dissemination channels		Status 12/22	
		Internal	External		
Management Board (Chairperson)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities: 6 Museums: 1 Libraries: 5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministries: 1 Funding bodies: nil Others: 4 	

Graphic: EOSC-KPIs: Socio-economic impact – Diversity. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Socio-economic Impact

National Collaboration

We build consensus and strengthen collaboration within Austrian institutions.

2022

Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Indicators		Methods		Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> active working groups EOSC SOA working group members EOSC SOA 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of groups number of persons (headcounts) 		all types	1 x per year
Source of data		Dissemination channels		Status 12/22	
		Internal	External		
Secretariat		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> coLAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Report 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 working groups 40 working group members (in total) 	

Graphic: EOSC-KPIs: Socio-economic impact – National Collaboration. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Socio-economic Impact

International Cooperation

We increase international cooperation in science and administration.

2022

Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> staff participating in or chairing EOOSC Association Task Forces joint projects with EOOSC Association members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of participants and chairs (headcounts) number of projects 	all types	1 x per year

Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
	Internal	External	
EOOSC Reference Points		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOOSC-A Reports and Monitoring Framework Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 participants in 12 from 13 EOOSC-A Task Forces, 2 of them Task Force chairs (in total 7 organisations) 2 joint projects of EOOSC SOA partners with EOOSC Association members (Skills4EOOSC, EOOSC Focus)

Graphic: EOOSC-KPIs: Socio-economic impact – International Collaboration. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Socio-economic Impact

Third-party Funding

We increase the third-party funding for EOOSC-dedicated e-infrastructures and services.

2022

Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partners receiving funding for e-infrastructures and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of partners funding amount 	all types	1 x per year

Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
	Internal	External	
FFG / FWF on behalf of the BMBWF or FFG-Monitor Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshops presentations 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Austrian EOOSC Association members received € 1.837.663 funding from the EC 4 of them are also partners of the EOOSC SOA and received € 1.257.163

Graphic: EOOSC-KPIs: Socio-economic impact – Third-party Funding. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Political Impact

2022

Starting point of monitoring, evaluation, assessment

Advocacy for EOSC

We work closely together with the Austrian ministries and other policy making institutions thus advocating for the EOSC.

Indicators		Methods		Types of institutions	Data collection frequency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. BMBWF) policy advice to streamline the direction of funding calls 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. Parlamentarisches Frühstück) 		all types	1 x per year

Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
	Internal	External	
Secretariat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e-mail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshop reports newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 inquiries from politics (BMBWF)

Graphic: EOSC-KPIs: Political Impact – Advocacy for EOSC. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

EOOSC-KPIs: Overview at the SOA-level

Objectives	Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency	Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/22
						Internal	External	
<p>Community Building We align institutions through our Austrian EOOSC partnership and implement support in our institutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partners of EOOSC SOA EOOSC reference points in partner institutions research support activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of signatories of the MoU number of reference points (headcounts) number of workshops, webinars, engagement activities 	all types	1 x per year	Management Board (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> colAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 ordinary partners 7 extraordinary partners 12 EOOSC reference points in these institutions 8 webinars, workshops and engagement activities
<p>Coordination The EOOSC Support Office Austria coordinates the national partnership efficiently.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> standardised processes transparent voting regular meetings Back office staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> review of processes and structures frequency of internal meetings number of back office staff in FTEs 	all types	Evaluation period April 2023	Management Board (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> colAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 standardised processes 1 transparent voting process 44 regular meetings (in total) 15 FTEs back office staff funded by the BMBWF for 3 years (01.07.2022-30.06.2025)
<p>Diversity We strengthen diversity within the EOOSC Support Office Austria.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> diversity of partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> qualitative description of the role and relevance of the partners Social Network Analysis (SNA) 	all types	Every third year	Management Board (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> names of institutions, types, expertise persons involved in all bodies by gender (f/m/d)
<p>National Collaboration We build consensus and strengthen collaboration within Austrian institutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> active working groups EOOSC SOA working group members EOOSC SOA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of groups number of persons (headcounts) 	all types	1 x per year	Secretariat (Chairperson)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> colAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Report 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 working groups 40 working group members (in total)
<p>International Cooperation We increase international cooperation in science and administration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> staff participating in or chairing EOOSC Association Task Forces joint projects with EOOSC Association members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of participants and chairs (headcounts) number of projects 	all types	1 x per year	EOOSC Reference Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOOSC-A Reports and Monitoring Framework Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOOSC-A Reports and Monitoring Framework Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 participants in 12 from 13 EOOSC Association Task Forces, 2 of them Task Force chairs (in total 7 organisations) 2 joint projects of EOOSC SOA partners with EOOSC Association members (Skills4EOOSC, EOOSC Focus)
<p>Third-party Funding We increase the third-party funding for EOOSC-dedicated e-infrastructures and services.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partners receiving funding for e-infrastructures and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of partners funding amount 	all types	1 x per year	FFG / FWF on behalf of the BMBWF or FFG-Monitor Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshops presentations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshops presentations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Austrian EOOSC Association members received € 1,837,663 funding from the EC 4 of them are also partners of the EOOSC SOA and received € 1,257,163
<p>Advocacy for EOOSC We work closely together with the Austrian ministries and other policy making institutions thus advocating for the EOOSC.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. BMBWF) policy advice to streamline the direction of funding calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. Parlamentarisches Fraktion) 	all types	1 x per year	Secretariat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e-mail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshop reports newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 inquiries from politics (BMBWF)

● Scientific Impact
 ● Socio-economic impact
 ● Political Impact

Graphic: EOOSC-KPIs: Objectives at the SOA-level. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic)

Annex A

Data repositories/data centers/data portals

At the moment, 55 "Austrian" repositories are registered by OpenDOAR (https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/view/repository_by_country/Austria.html) and 45 data repositories by re3data ([https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries\[\]=AUT](https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries[]=AUT)).

Below there is an excerpt of available data repositories and/or data centres in Austria (NB: not all listed on the re3data platform).

Name of repository	Type (repository/ data centre/data portal)	Link	Comment
Cross-disciplinary/Institutional			
Data Repository of the International Institute of Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA-DARE)	Repository	http://dare.iiasa.ac.at/	
Digital Repository KUG-PHAIDRA (University of Music and Performing Arts Graz – KUG)	Repository	https://phaidra.kug.ac.at/	
Institutional Repository of the University of Art and Design Linz	Repository	https://phaidra.ufg.at/	
Institutional Repository of the University of Applied Arts	Repository	https://phaidra.bibliothek.uni-ak.ac.at/	
IST Austria Research Explorer	Repository	https://research-explorer.app.ist.ac.at	
PHAIDRA @ FH St Pölten	Repository	https://phaidra.fhstp.ac.at/	
mdw Repository	Repository	https://repo.mdw.ac.at	
Phaidra - Repository of the University of Veterinary Medicine, Vienna	Repository	https://phaidra.vetmeduni.ac.at	
TU Graz Repository	Repository	https://repository.tugraz.at/	
TU Wien Research Data	Repository	https://researchdata.tuwien.at	
Universität Innsbruck - Data Repository	Repository	https://researchdata.uibk.ac.at	
University of Vienna PHAIDRA	Repository	https://phaidra.univie.ac.at	
Discipline specific			
ARCHE - A Resource Centre for the HumanitiEs	Repository	https://arche.acdh.oeaw.ac.at	Core Trust Seal (CTS)
AUSSDA Dataverse	Repository	https://data.aussda.at/	Core Trust Seal (CTS)
CCCA - Climate Change Center Austria	Repository	https://data.ccca.ac.at	

EODC - Earth Observation Data Centre	Data centre	https://www.eodc.eu/	
Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System (GAMS)	Repository	https://gams.uni-graz.at	Core Trust Seal (CTS)
NHM Forschungsdaten-Repository	Repository	http://datarepository.nhm-wien.ac.at	
Tethys - Geologische Bundesanstalt (GBA), Data Publisher for Geoscience Austria	Repository	https://www.tethys.at/	
Topic specific			
Thanados - The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures	Repository	https://thanados.net/	
Public Sector Information			
Open Data Austria - data.gv.at	Repository	https://www.data.gv.at/	Central Austrian portal for public sector data. Data are provided to European portal data.europa.eu
Open Data Portal Austria	Data portal	https://www.opendataportal.at	Central platform for open data in the areas of business, culture, NGO/NPO, research and civil society in Austria
ZAMG Data Hub	Repository	https://data.hub.zamg.ac.at/	Metadata exchanged with the portal Open Data Austria (data.gv.at)
Mobilitätsdaten Österreich	Data portal	https://mobilitaetsdaten.gv.at/	Mobility data
INSPIRE Österreich	Data portal	https://www.inspire.gv.at/	Austrian spatial data infrastructure
AMDC - Austrian Micro Data Center	Data centre	https://www.statistik.at/services/tools/services/amdc-mikrodaten-fuer-die-wissenschaft	Data only available via Remote Research Environment of Statistik Austria for a limited period of time
Other			
Austrian State Archives	Data centre	http://www.oesta.gv.at/	

BRZ - Austrian Federal Computing Center	Data centre	https://en.brz.gv.at/	
Statistik Austria	Data centre	https://www.statistik.at/	
Vorarlberger Landesbibliothek - Volare	Repository	https://pid.volare.vorarlberg.at/	

Annex B

Publication/document servers

At the moment, 55 "Austrian" repositories are registered by OpenDOAR (https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/view/repository_by_country/Austria.html) and 45 data repositories by re3data ([https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries\[\]=AUT](https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries[]=AUT)).

NB: Not all existing repositories are registered in a directory.

Name of repository	Link	Comment
Institutional publication/document servers		
Ja[repository	https://repository.akbild.ac.at	
BOKU:epub	http://epub.boku.ac.at/	
DOOR	https://door.donau-uni.ac.at/	
Austrian Institute for Health Technology Assessment Repository for Publications	https://eprints.aihta.at/	Former known as LBI HTA
Elektronisches Publikationsportal der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften	http://epub.oeaw.ac.at/	
ePLUS (Open Access Publikationsserver der Universität Salzburg)	http://eplus.uni-salzburg.at	
ePubWU Institutional Repository (ePubWU)	http://epub.wu.ac.at	
FHpub	https://fhpub.fh-vie.ac.at	
FWF-E-Book-Library	https://e-book.fwf.ac.at/	
IIASA PURE	http://pure.iiasa.ac.at/	
INIS Repository	http://inis.iaea.org/search	
IRIHS - Institutional Repository at IHS	https://irihs.ihs.ac.at	
IST Austria Research Explorer	https://research-explorer.app.ist.ac.at	
Institutional Repository of the Mozarteum University	http://repository.moz.ac.at	
JKU ePub	http://epub.jku.at/	
Kirchlicher DokumentenServer der AKThB und des VkwB (KiDokS)	https://kidoks.bsz-bw.de/home	
MedUni Wien ePub	https://repositorium.meduniwien.ac.at	
Online Publikationsserver der Fachhochschule Vorarlberg	https://opus.fhv.at	
People @ FH Burgenland	https://people.fh-burgenland.at/	
Publication Database of the Vienna University of Technology	https://publik.tuwien.ac.at/start.php?lang=2	

Publikationsserver der Universität Klagenfurt (netlibrary)	https://netlibrary.aau.at/	
pub.mdw - Open Access Publication Server	https://pub.mdw.ac.at	
repositUm (TU Wien Open Access Plattform)	https://repositum.tuwien.at	
TUGraz OPEN Library	http://openlib.tugraz.at/	
University of Innsbruck Digital Library	http://diglib.uibk.ac.at/	
u:scholar	http://uscholar.univie.ac.at/	
uni≡pub (unipub)	http://unipub.uni-graz.at/	
Phaidra (@University of Vienna)	https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/	
State and county library servers		
Digitale Landesbibliothek Oberösterreich	http://digi.landesbibliothek.at/	
Discipline specific publication/document servers		
Architektur-Informatik	http://architektur-informatik.scix.net/cgi-bin/works/Home	
CumInCAD Digital Archive	http://cumincad.architexturez.net/	
Elektronisch archivierte Theorie - Sammelpunkt	http://sammelpunkt.philo.at:8080/	
Fluorophores.org	http://www.fluorophores.tugraz.at/	
PiezoMat.org	http://www.PiezoMat.org/	
RISC Publications	https://risc.jku.at/publications/	
Other		
Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation (fteval)	https://repository.fteval.at	
European Research Papers Archive (ERPA)	http://eiop.or.at/erpa/	